

Synthesis of Oxygenated Coumestans

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Eight oxygenated coumestans and their acetates have been prepared by dehydrative cyclisation of 4-hydroxy-3-arylcoumarins using methanolic hydrogen chloride. Their spectral characteristics and useful physiological properties have been presented.

In our earlier communication¹, a facile synthesis of oxygenated 3-aryl-4-hydroxycoumarins has been reported. The synthesis involved condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin derivatives with *p*-benzoquinone and the product 4-hydroxy-3-*p*-benzoquinonylcoumarin derivative formed was subsequently converted into oxygenated 4-hydroxy-3-arylcoumarins by acetylation and hydrolysis. In the present communication, the product obtained by dehydrative cyclisation of 4-hydroxy-3-arylcoumarins using methanolic hydrogen chloride has been characterised by spectral data as coumestans. Eight new oxygenated coumestans and their acetates have been prepared. Their spectral data and useful physiological properties have been presented.

It has been observed that coumestans exhibit varied physiological properties, *viz.* estrogenic²⁻⁶, phytoalexin⁷, and antibacterial activities⁸. The naturally occurring coumestans contain variety of hydroxylation pattern having resorcinol, quinol, hydroxyquinol, phloroglucinol and pyrogallol nucleus⁹. Since the polyhydroxycoumestans have biogenetic significance, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise the new polyhydroxycoumestans and evaluate their activity.

In the present investigation, 4,5-dihydroxy-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl)coumarin (1)¹ was dissolved in methanol, saturated with dehydrogen chloride gas and later refluxed (10 h). The green coloured compound exhibited m. p. > 300°; green colour with ferric chloride; single spot on tlc (silica gel G, ethyl acetate); λ_{max} 235 (log ϵ 4.4, benzofuranylchromophore), 285 (4.1) and 340 nm (4.27, cinnamoyl chromophore); ν_{max} 3 200 (-OH) and 1 690 cm^{-1} (coumarin C=O). As the compound was found insoluble in most of the organic solvents, its acetate was prepared (3), ν_{max} 1 750 (acetate C=O) and 1 690 cm^{-1} (coumarin C=O); δ 2.35 (6H, s, two acetate), 2.53 (3H, s, one acetate) and 7.29-7.78 (3H, m, aromatic protons). On the basis of the above spectral data, the product 3 has been assigned 1,8,9-triacetoxycoumestan structure (Chart 1) and the parent hydroxy coumestan has structure 2.

Chart 1

The mass spectrum of 3 showed parent ion peak at m/z 410. The loss of three ketene units was indicated by an ion at m/z 284 which constituted a base peak in the mass spectrum. Two successive losses of CO from the latter ion was represented by two ions at m/z 256 and 228. All these and other ions and their possible structures have been presented in Chart 2.

Chart 2

The compound 2 was also prepared following Wanzlick's¹⁰ procedure. The process involved

condensation of 4,5-dihydroxycoumarin¹¹ with catechol in the presence of sodium acetate and potassium ferricyanide in aqueous acetone medium giving rise to **2** which was subsequently acetylated with acetic anhydride and pyridine to **3**. The triacetate obtained by this route was found identical in all respects with the one obtained by cyclisation of **1** (identical m.p., m.m.p. undepressed and superimposable ir spectra). Compound **2** was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and the methyl ether formed was identical in all respects with 1,8,9-trimethoxycoumestan obtained earlier¹² (m.m.p. undepressed and ir spectra superimposable).

4,5-Dihydroxy-3-(2',5'-dihydroxyphenyl) coumarin (**4**) was dissolved in methanol, saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas and refluxed (10 h). A light green coloured compound **5** was formed, m.p. > 300°; violet green colour with ferric chloride; single spot on tlc (silica gel G, ethyl acetate); $\lambda_{\max}$ 236 (log ϵ 4.38, benzofuranyl chromophore), 288 (4.20), 345 nm (4.29, cinnamoyl chromophore); $\nu_{\max}$ 3300 (OH) and 1690 cm^{-1} (coumarin C=O). The spectral data was in agreement with the earlier data on coumestans. On the basis of above spectral data, the compound has been assigned as 1,8-

Chart 3

dihydroxycoumestan (**5**). The assigned structure (**5**) was further supported by the pmr and mass spectral data of its diacetate (**6**), $\nu_{\max}$ 1750 (acetate C=O) and 1685 cm^{-1} (coumestan C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 2.2 (3H, s, 8-OAc), 2.5 (3H, s, 1-OAc) and 7.2–7.6 (6H, m, aromatic protons). On the basis of the above spectral data, the diacetate has been assigned as 1,8-diacetoxycoumestan (**6**). The mass spectrum indicated molecular ion at m/z 352. Two ketene units were lost from M^+ giving rise to ion at m/z 268. Two successive losses of CO was further indicated by two ions at m/z 240 and 212 (Chart 4).

Chart 4

Adopting the above procedure, 2,8,9-trihydroxycoumestan, 3,8,9-trihydroxycoumestan, 1,3,8,9-tetrahydroxycoumestan (these three coumestans were also prepared by Wanzlick's procedure), 2,8-dihydroxycoumestan, 3,8-dihydroxycoumestan and 1,3,8-trihydroxycoumestans have been prepared from 4,6-dihydroxycoumarin¹³, 4,7-dihydroxycoumarin¹⁴ and 4,5,7-trihydroxycoumarin¹⁵, respectively. All these compounds have been obtained in good yields (51–58%). They have been converted into the corresponding acetates with acetic anhydride and pyridine. Their physical, analytical and spectral data have been presented in Table 1.

The coumestans synthesised have been screened for their antibacterial (tube dilution method) and antifungal (plate method) activities. All the compounds were found active. The most active among the compounds tested for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* was 1,8,9-trihydroxycoumestan at 10 ppm level. The most active among the compounds tested for antifungal activity against *A. niger* at 100 ppm level were 1,3,8,9-tetraacetoxycoumestan (showed 56% inhibition) and 1,3,8,9-tetrahydroxycoumestan (50% inhibition) and 1,8,9-triacetoxycoumestan (48% inhibition).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in an open capillaries and are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded in methanol on a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer, ir spectra recorded with KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (in CDCl_3) on Varian-A 60D spectrometer (chemical shifts downfield from TMS), and mass spectra on a Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi RUM-6L double focussing spectrometer operating at 70 eV using direct inlet system.

General procedure: 1,8,9-Trihydroxycoumestan (**2**): 4,5-Dihydroxy-3-(2',4',5'-trihydroxyphenyl) coumarin (**1**) (1.5 g) was dissolved in methanol (30 ml) and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas at 0° for 2 h. The solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. A green coloured solid separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from acetone, (59%) m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 63.36; H, 2.80. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$ required for: C, 63.38; H, 2.81%).

Alternate procedure (2)¹²: 4,5-Dihydroxycoumarin (1.78 g) and catechol (1.10 g) were dissolved in aqueous acetone (1:1, 20 ml) and sodium acetate (**6** g) was then added. To this solution, a solution of potassium ferricyanide (6 g) and sodium acetate (2 g) in water (20 ml) was added dropwise while shaking. During the process of addition crystals of **2** separated. After the addition was over, the product formed was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from acetone, (1.85 g, 65%), m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 63.40; H, 2.83. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$ required for: C, 63.38; H, 2.81%).

1,8,9-Triacetoxycoumestan (3): **2** (0.70 g) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (5 ml) and two drops

TABLE I—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COUMESTANS

Sl no.	Substituent	M p °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		λ_{max} (log ϵ) nm	ν_{OH} cm ⁻¹	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm ⁻¹
					C	H			
1.	1,8-Dihydroxy	200	68	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₂	67.14 (67.16)	2.96 (2.98)	286 (4.98) 288 (4.20) 345 (4.29)	3300	1690
2.	1,8-Diacetoxy	235	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₆	64.73 (64.77)	3.42 (3.41)	—	—	1695 1750
3.	2,8-Dihydroxy	800	52	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₂	67.12 (67.16)	2.99 (2.98)	240 (4.43) 273 (4.06) 348 (4.22)	3350	1680
4.	2,8-Diacetoxy	258	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₆	64.79 (64.77)	3.37 (3.41)	—	—	—
5.	3,8-Dihydroxy	305	67	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₂	67.11 (67.16)	2.95 (2.98)	235 (4.45) 275 (4.09) 345 (4.21)	3350	1650
6.	3,8-Diacetoxy	240	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ O ₆	64.80 (64.77)	3.40 (3.41)	—	—	—
7.	1,3,8-Trihydroxy	304	53	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₃	63.40 (63.38)	2.79 (2.81)	240 (4.11) 290 (4.12) 348 (4.25)	3350	1650
8.	1,3,8-Triacetoxy	249	62	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₆	61.47 (61.46)	3.40 (3.41)	—	—	—
9.	1,8,9-Trihydroxy	>300	59	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₃	63.36 (63.38)	2.80 (2.81)	235 (4.41) 285 (4.10) 340 (4.27)	3200	1690
10.	1,8,9-Triacetoxy	248	63	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₆	61.45 (61.46)	3.42 (3.41)	—	—	1690 1750
11.	2,8,9-Trihydroxy	>300	58	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₃	63.39 (63.38)	2.79 (2.81)	235 (4.42) 278 (4.09) 335 (4.20)	3200	1700
12.	2,8,9-Triacetoxy	268	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₆	61.44 (61.46)	3.39 (3.41)	—	—	—
13.	3,8,9-Trihydroxy	>300	52	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₃	63.36 (63.38)	2.78 (2.81)	240 (4.38) 270 (4.08) 345 (4.20)	3250	1700
14.	3,8,9-Triacetoxy	265	71	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₆	61.47 (61.46)	3.39 (3.41)	—	—	—
15.	1,3,8,9-Tetrahydroxy	>300	55	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₄	59.90 (60.00)	2.65 (2.66)	245 (4.40) 275 (4.10) 330 (4.28)	3300	1690
16.	1,3,8,9-Tetraacetoxy	259	67	C ₂₁ H ₁₀ O ₁₁	58.95 (59.98)	3.43 (3.42)	—	—	—

of pyridine added. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h and later worked out in the usual manner. The triacetate (3) was recrystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (63%), m.p. 243° (Found. C, 61.45; H, 3.42. C₂₁H₁₄O₆ requires for : C, 61.46; H, 3.41%).

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